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Design and Evaluation of Extended Release Capsules of Acetazolamide Using Eudragit RS100 And Eudragit RL100

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ABSTRACT

Utilizing the concept of incorporating drug in to the polymer matrices and extend the drug release for prolong period of time, an attempt was made to design and evaluate extended release capsules of acetazolamide using extended release polymers. The initial three formulations of Acetazolamide ER capsules were formulated with Ethyl cellulose N-7, Benecel (HPMC 15M) and Natrosol (HHX Pharm) with concentrations of 11%, 13% and 15% respectively. However satisfactory results were not obtained these polymers and it was decided to proceed further with high viscosity polymers which would effectively sustain the release of drug. The F1 - F16 batches were taken with different concentrations of Eudragit RS100 and Eudragit RL100. The combinations of these polymers in different proportions provide varied sustained release profiles. The optimized formulation (F12) was developed by using Eudragit RS100 (6%) and Eudragit RL100 (4%). The dissolution profiles of formulation F12 and innovator product were compared by calculating differential factor (f1) and similarity factor (f2). The f1 and f2 were found to be 2.97 and 69.70 respectively for the comparison of dissolution profiles of formulation F12 and innovator product. Infrared Spectroscopy studies were showed sharp characteristic peaks for Acetazolamide at different wave numbers. All the above peaks appeared in optimised formulation at same wave numbers, indicating no interaction between the drug and the polymer. The stability studies on Acetazolamide ER capsules 500 mg in HDPE container at 40°C / 75 % RH were conducted as per ICH protocol and no significant change was observed in the assay value after a storage period of 1 month at 40°C / 75 % RH and 2 months at 40°C / 75 % RH.

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INTRODUCTION:

Acetazolamide is a synthetic carbonic anhydrase inhibitor, effective in the control of fluid secretion. It is used in the preoperative management of closed-angle glaucoma, or as an adjunct in the treatment of open-angle glaucoma and edema due to congestive heart failure, drug-induced edema and centrencephalic epilepsies. Acetazolamide is rapidly and almost completely absorbed from the GI tract ($\approx 100\%$), reaching peak plasma concentrations

approximately 1–3 hrs after oral administration. The human first order absorption rate constant is reported to be 0.821 h^{-1} . It irreversibly inhibits the enzyme carbonic anhydrase resulting in reduction of hydrogen ion secretion at renal tubules and an increased renal excretion of sodium, potassium, bicarbonate and water to decrease production of aqueous humor. It also inhibits carbonic anhydrase in central nervous system to retard abnormal and excessive discharge from CNS neurons^{1,2}.

Fig 1.1 - A hypothetical plasma concentration-time profile from conventional multiple dosing and single doses of sustained and controlled delivery formulations. (MSC = maximum safe concentration, MEC = minimum effective concentration).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials used: Acetazolamide (Nakoda Chemicals, Hyderabad), Avicel PH 101 and Avicel PH 102 (Loba Chemie Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai), Benecel HPMC 15M and Natrosol HHX Pharm (Gift sample from Aqualon, USA), Ethyl cellulose N 7 - 7 cps, Ethyl cellulose N 14 - 14 cps and Ethyl cellulose N22 - 22 cps (Chemo India, Mumbai), Povidone K 90, HPMC E- 5, HPMC E - 15 and SLS (Signet Chemical Corporation, Mumbai), Eudragit NE 40D, Eudragit RS 30D, Eudragit RL 30D, Eudragit RS 100, Eudragit RL 100, Eudragit EPO (Gift sample from Degussa (Germany), Talc (Qualikems Fine Chemicals Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi).

PREFORMULATION STUDIES

Preformulation testing is an investigation of physical and chemical properties of a drug substance alone and when combined with excipients. It is the first step in the rational development of dosage forms. Preformulation commences when a newly synthesized drug shows sufficient pharmacologic promise in animal models to warrant evaluation in man. These studies focus on those physicochemical properties of the new compound that could affect drug performance and development of an efficacious dosage form. A thorough understanding of these properties may ultimately provide a rationale for formulation design, or support the need for molecular modification^{3,4}.

Angle of Repose

The angle of repose is the maximum angle that the plane of powder makes with the horizontal surface on rotation. Angle of repose is helpful in assessment of flow properties of particles which could be further related to packing densities and mechanical arrangements of particles. The angle of repose of granules was determined by the fixed funnel and free standing cone method. The accurately weighed granules were taken in a funnel. The height of the funnel was adjusted in such a manner that the tip of the funnel just touched the apex of the heap of the granules. The granules were allowed to flow through the funnel freely onto the surface. The diameter of the powder cone measured and angle of repose was calculated using the following equation: $\tan \theta = h/r$, Where, h = height of the powder heap, r = radius of the powder heap, θ = is the angle of repose.

Determination of Bulk Density and Tapped Density

Bulk density of a compound varies substantially with the method of crystallization, milling or formulation. It is of great importance when one considers the size of a high – dose capsule product or the homogeneity of a low dose formulation in which there are large differences in drug and excipient densities. In addition to bulk density, it is frequently desirable to know the true density of a powder for computation of void volume or porosity of packed powder beds.

An accurately weighed quantity of the granules / powder (W) was carefully poured into the graduated cylinder and volume (V_0) was measured. Then the

graduated cylinder was closed with lid and set into the tap density tester (USP). The density apparatus was set for 100 tabs and after that the volume (V_f) was measured and continued operation till the two consecutive readings were equal. The bulk density and the tapped density were calculated using the following formulae: Bulk density = W/V_0 , Tapped density = W/V_f , Where, W= Weight of the powder, V_0 = Initial volume, V_f = final volume.

Hausner's Ratio

Hausner's Ratio indicates the flow properties of the powder and is measured by the ratio of tapped density to bulk density. It is the ratio of tapped density and bulk density. Hausner's found that this ratio was related to inter-particle friction and, as such, could be used to predict powder flow properties. Generally a value less than 1.25 indicates good flow properties, which is equivalent to 20% of Carr's index. Hausner's Ratio = Tapped density / Bulk Density.

Sieve analysis

The main aim of sieve analysis is to determine the different size of drug particles present. A series of standard sieves were stacked one above the other so that sieves with larger pore size (less sieve number) occupy top position followed by sieves of decreasing pore size (larger sieve number) towards the bottom. A series of sieves were arranged in the order of decreasing pore diameter. 100g of API was weighed accurately and transferred to sieve on the top. The sieves were shaken for about 10 minutes. Then the drug retained on each sieve was taken,

weighed separately and expressed in terms of percentage weight retained.

Solubility studies:

The solubility of API was determined by dissolving the highest unit dose of the drug in 250 mL of buffer adjusted between pH 1.0 and 8.0. For this purpose 0.1N HCl, pH 4.6 buffer, pH 6.8 buffer and purified water were used. Highest dose of the drug i.e., 500 mg was dissolved in 250 mL of medium and was kept untouched for 6 hrs. Later on the insoluble drug was filtered off and the solution was analysed by HPLC technique to find out the solubility. Based on the solubility calculated the D/S ratios were calculated. The FDA guidance on "Dissolution Testing of Immediate Release Solid Oral Dosage Forms" says that a drug substance is considered highly soluble when the dose/solubility volume of solution are less than or equal to 250 mL^{5,6}.

PROCEDURES^{7,8}

F1: Accurately weigh Acetazolamide and Avicel PH 101 and pass through sieve #40 and blend for 10 mins. Prepare granulating solution by dispersing ethyl cellulose in specified quantity of isopropyl alcohol and stir under a stirrer till a clear solution is formed. Add this binder solution to the previously prepared dry blend of drug and MCC and granulate. Pass the wet granules through sieve #12 and dry. Pass the dried granules through sieve #20. Add talc and sodium lauryl sulphate which were previously passed through sieve#40 to the dried granules blend, blend for 5 mins. The granules were filled in "00" size capsules.

F2: Accurately weigh Acetazolamide, Avicel PH 101 and Benecel (HPMC 15M) and pass through sieve #40 and blend thoroughly for 10 mins. To the above blend add required quantity of purified water and granulate. Pass the wet granules through sieve #12 and dry. Pass the dried granules through sieve #20. Add talc and sodium lauryl sulphate which were previously passed through sieve#40 to the dried granules blend, blend for 5 mins. The granules were filled in “00” size capsules.

F3: Accurately weigh Acetazolamide, Avicel PH 101 and Ethyl cellulose and pass through sieve #40 and blend thoroughly for 10 mins. To the above blend add required quantity of purified water and granulate. Pass the wet granules through sieve #12 and dry. Pass the dried granules through sieve #20. Add talc and sodium lauryl sulphate which were previously passed through sieve#40 to the dried granules blend, blend for 5 mins. The granules were filled in “00” size capsules.

F4: Accurately weigh Acetazolamide, Avicel PH 101 and Natrosol (HHX Pharm) and pass through sieve #40 and blend thoroughly for 10 mins. Prepare granulating solution by dispersing accurately weighed quantity of Povidone K-90 in specified quantity of purified water and stir under a stirrer till a clear solution is formed. Add this binder solution to the previously prepared dry blend of drug, avicel and Natrosol and granulate. Pass the wet granules through sieve #12 and dry. Pass the dried granules through sieve #20. Add talc and sodium lauryl sulphate which were previously passed through sieve#40 to the dried granules blend, blend for 5 mins. The granules were filled in “00” size capsules.

F5: Accurately weigh Acetazolamide, Avicel PH 101 and HPMC E15 and pass through sieve #40 and blend thoroughly for 10 mins. Prepare granulating solution by dispersing accurately weighed quantity of Povidone K-90 in specified quantity of purified water and stir under a stirrer till a clear solution is formed. Add this binder solution to the previously prepared dry blend of drug, avicel and HPMC E15 and granulate. Pass the wet granules through sieve #12 and dry. Pass the dried granules through sieve #20. Add talc and sodium lauryl sulphate which were previously passed through sieve#40 to the dried granules blend, blend for 5 mins. The granules were filled in “00” size capsules.

F6: Accurately weigh Acetazolamide and Avicel PH 101 pass through sieve #40 and blend thoroughly for 10 mins. Weigh accurately the specified quantity of Eudragit NE 40D in a tarred beaker. Add this granulating medium to the previously prepared dry blend of drug and avicel and granulate. Pass the wet granules through sieve #10 and dry at 60-65°C. Pass the dried granules through sieve #20. Add talc and sodium lauryl sulphate which were previously passed through sieve#40 to the dried granules blend, blend for 5 mins. The granules were filled in “00” size capsules.

F7: Accurately weigh Acetazolamide and Avicel PH 101 and pass through sieve #40 and blend thoroughly for 10 mins. Add talc and sodium lauryl sulphate which were previously passed through sieve#40 to the previously prepared blend of drug and avicel, blend for 5 mins. The granules were filled in “00” size capsules.

F8: Accurately weigh Acetazolamide and Avicel PH 102 and pass through sieve #40 and blend thoroughly for 10 mins. Add talc and sodium lauryl sulphate which were previously passed through sieve#40 to the previously prepared blend of drug and avicel, blend for 5 mins. The granules were filled in “00” size capsules.

F9: Accurately weigh Acetazolamide, Avicel PH 101 and HPMC E5 and pass through sieve #40 and blend thoroughly for 10 mins. Weigh accurately the specified quantity of Eudragit RL 30D in a tared beaker. Add this granulating medium to the previously prepared dry blend of drug, avicel, and HPMC E5 and granulate. Pass the wet granules through sieve #10 and dry. Pass the dried granules through sieve #30. Add talc and sodium lauryl sulphate which were previously passed through sieve#40 to the dried granules blend and it was blend for 5 mins. Fill the granules in “00” size capsules.

F10: Accurately weigh Acetazolamide, Avicel PH 101 and HPMC E5 and pass through sieve #40 and blend thoroughly for 10 mins. Weigh accurately the specified quantity of Eudragit RS 30D (10%) in a tared beaker. Add this granulating medium to the previously prepared dry blend of drug, avicel, and HPMC E5 and granulate. Pass the wet granules through sieve #10 and dry. Pass the dried granules through sieve #30. Add talc and sodium lauryl sulphate which were previously passed through sieve#40 to the dried granules blend, blend for 5 mins. The granules were filled in “00” size capsules.

F11: Accurately weigh Acetazolamide and Avicel PH 101 and pass through sieve #40 and blend

thoroughly for 10 mins. Weigh accurately the specified quantities of Eudragit RS 100 (7%) and Eudragit RL 100 (3%) and add to 70mL of acetone and 10mL of isopropyl alcohol mixture in a beaker. Stir for 30 mins until a clear solution is formed. Add this granulating medium to the previously prepared dry blend of drug and avicel and granulate. Pass the wet granules through sieve #12 and dry. Pass the dried granules through sieve #30. Add talc and sodium lauryl sulphate which were previously passed through sieve#40 to the dried granules blend, blend for 5 mins. The granules were filled in “00” size capsules.

F12: Accurately weigh Acetazolamide and Avicel PH 101 and pass through sieve #40 and blend thoroughly for 10 mins. Weigh accurately the specified quantities of Eudragit RS 100 (5%) and Eudragit RL 100 (5%) and add to 60mL of acetone and 30mL of isopropyl alcohol mixture in a beaker. Stir for 30 mins until a clear solution is formed. Add this granulating medium to the previously prepared dry blend of drug and avicel and granulate. Pass the wet granules through sieve #12 and dry. Pass the dried granules through sieve #30. Add talc and sodium lauryl sulphate which were previously passed through sieve#40 to the dried granules blend, blend for 5 mins. The granules were filled in “00” size capsules.

F13: Accurately weigh Acetazolamide and Avicel PH 101 and pass through sieve #40 and blend thoroughly for 10 mins. Weigh accurately the specified quantities of Eudragit RS 100 (3%) and Eudragit RL 100 (7%) and add to 60mL of acetone and 10mL of isopropyl alcohol mixture in a beaker.

Stir for 30 mins until a clear solution is formed. Add this granulating medium to the previously prepared dry blend of drug and avicel and granulate. Pass the wet granules through sieve #12 and dry. Pass the dried granules through sieve #30. Add talc and sodium lauryl sulphate which were previously passed through sieve#40 to the dried granules blend and it was blend for 5 mins. The granules were filled in “00” size capsules.

F14: Accurately weigh Acetazolamide and Avicel PH 101 and pass through sieve #40 and blend thoroughly for 10 mins. Weigh accurately the specified quantities of Eudragit RS 100 (9%) and Eudragit RL 100 (1%) and add to 60mL of acetone and 60mL of isopropyl alcohol mixture in a beaker. Stir for 30 mins until a clear solution is formed. Add this granulating medium to the previously prepared dry blend of drug and avicel and granulate. Pass the wet granules through sieve #12 and dry. Pass the dried granules through sieve #30. Add talc and sodium lauryl sulphate which were previously passed through sieve#40 to the dried granules blend. Blend for 5 mins and the granules were filled in “00” size capsules.

F15: Accurately weigh Acetazolamide and Avicel PH 101 and pass through sieve #40 and blend thoroughly for 10 mins. Weigh accurately the specified quantity of Eudragit RS 100 (10%) and add to 60mL of acetone and 10mL of isopropyl alcohol mixture in a beaker. Stir for 30 minutes until a clear solution is formed. Add this granulating medium to the previously prepared dry blend of drug and avicel and granulate. Pass the wet granules through sieve #12 and dry. Pass the dried granules

through sieve #30. Add talc and sodium lauryl sulphate which were previously passed through sieve#40 to the dried granules blend. Blend for 5 mins and the granules were filled in “00” size capsules.

F16: Accurately weigh Acetazolamide and Avicel PH 101 and pass through sieve #40 and blend thoroughly for 10 mins. Weigh accurately the specified quantity of Eudragit RS 100 (5%) and Eudragit EPO (5%) and add to 60 mL of acetone and 60 mL of isopropyl alcohol mixture in a beaker. Stir for 30 mins until a clear solution is formed. Add this granulating medium to the previously prepared dry blend of drug and avicel and granulate. Pass the wet granules through sieve #12 and dry. Pass the dried granules through sieve #30. Add talc and sodium lauryl sulphate which were previously passed through sieve#40 to the dried granules blend. Blend for 5 mins and the granules were filled in “00” size capsules.

ACCELERATED STABILITY STUDIES

The stability studies on Acetazolamide ER capsules 500 mg in HDPE container at 40⁰C / 75 % RH for 2 months were conducted as per ICH protocol. After the specified time period (1 month and 2 months), the samples were unloaded from the stability chambers and were tested for any physical or chemical changes. Also the tests for dissolution and assay were conducted to assess the stability of product^{9,10}.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:**Flow properties**

The API and the formulated granules were characterized with respect to angle of repose, bulk density and tapped density. Angle of repose of API was found to be 33.6°, thus indicating that the flow properties were poor (passable). For the granules of

all the formulated batches, the angle of repose was found to be in the range of 28° to 36°, thus indicating that the flow properties were fair - poor (passable). Hausner's ratio was more than 1.25 for all the batches indicating poor flow properties. Therefore it was decided to include 1.0% to 1.2% of Talc as a Glidant.

Table 1: Flow properties of the formulation F1- F16.

BATCH	BULK DENSITY(g/mL)	TAPPED DENSITY(g/mL)	ANGLE OF REPOSE (°)
API	0.70	0.601	33.6
F1	0.535	0.714	30.9
F2	0.515	0.647	32.5
F3	0.500	0.647	34.3
F4	0.555	0.673	31.2
F5	0.597	0.740	30.6
F6	0.520	0.657	33.4
F7	0.465	0.712	34.2
F8	0.333	0.691	28.2
F9	0.897	0.660	26.7
F10	0.636	0.777	24.3
F11	0.462	0.806	41.5
F12	0.510	0.806	35.5
F13	0.462	0.833	41.9
F14	0.500	0.657	35.5
F15	0.500	0.675	35.1
F16	0.526	0.789	30.7

Table 2: Weight variation and assay.

BATCH	AVERAGE WEIGHT*	ASSAY†
F1	766.8±2.48	98.25±1.37
F2	765±2.54	95.28±0.80
F3	768.6±2.41	99.12±2.47
F4	770.8±1.64	101.22±0.88
F5	767.6±2.14	100.24±1.25
F6	769.0±2.43	95.35±1.14
F7	770.5±1.80	96.34±2.18
F8	771.2±1.83	91.29±0.98
F9	771.1±1.97	97.35±0.43
F10	768.2±2.17	98.88±0.88
F11	766.0±2.22	102.55±2.15
F12	767.8±2.48	98.36±2.31
F13	768.4±2.04	93.78±1.56
F14	771.4±2.09	96.27±1.88
F15	770.7±2.65	92.55±1.56
F16	770.1±1.82	102.87±0.97

* Values represent mean ± Standard Deviation (SD), n=20

† Values represent mean ± Standard Deviation (SD), n=3

Table 3: Dissolution profiles†

BATCH	TIME (hrs)	0	1	3	6	9	12	20
INNOVATOR	0	14.7±1.2	33.2±0.9	65.7±1.1	83.3±1.3	91.9±1.6	98.2±1.4	
F1	0	26.5±2.6	36.1±2.9	45.8±1.8	62.2±2.2	73.5±1.9	84.4±2.4	
F2	0	24.2±2.1	37.9±1.4	40.3±1.9	66.1±2.2	70.8±2.0	82.2±1.7	
F3	0	33.2±1.6	40.1±2.1	56.7±2.3	68.2±1.9	78.5±2.1	97.2±2.2	
F4	0	80.7±2.1	97.9±2.3	98.8±1.6	97.9±2.4	97.6±1.9	97.5±1.8	
F5	0	41.26±1.8	62.1±2.1	77.9±1.6	82.3±1.4	83.8±1.7	85.2±1.7	
F6	0	13.5±2.1	19.9±1.8	26.9±2.2	31.8±2.3	35.7±1.9	41.8±1.6	
F7	0	16.0±2.4	25.6±2.1	31.9±1.8	36.6±1.6	55.3±1.7	65.8±1.9	
F8	0	5.8±1.8	15.0±2.1	22.7±1.9	28.1±2.4	32.5±2.1	42.9±1.8	
F9	0	7.0±1.9	16.0±2.3	22.6±1.6	28.3±1.8	32.7±2.0	36.6±2.3	
F10	0	25.7±2.2	41.7±1.8	55.8±2.7	67.0±2.3	76.1±1.6	85.4±1.9	
F11	0	15.4±2.3	29.0±1.8	42.1±2.6	53.1±2.5	76.5±2.3	81.9±1.7	
F12	0	18.2±2.4	30.4±1.6	61.9±1.7	79.8±2.0	86.4±1.7	96.1±1.4	
F13	0	29.1±2.0	47.9±1.6	84.2±2.4	97.2±1.9	97.8±1.5	101.2±2.1	
F14	0	44.6±1.5	90.4±1.8	97.0±1.6	97.3±2.1	96.4±2.0	95.0±1.6	
F15	0	12.0±2.3	36.2±2.6	54.8±1.8	76.7±2.4	76.2±2.2	84.7±1.7	
F16	0	6.7±1.9	12.9±2.2	17.7±1.7	22.4±2.3	26.2±2.0	33.7±1.6	

† Values represent mean ± Standard Deviation (SD), n=6

The Acetazolamide ER capsules were formulated with high viscosity polymers which would effectively sustain the release of drug. The effect of these polymers on the release of acetazolamide is shown in the following graph (**Fig. 1**). The F4 batch was formulated with HPMC E15 (4%) and Povidone K-90 (5%). However the release was more from the

dosage form and it was decided to replace HPMC E15 with high viscosity polymer Ethyl cellulose N-22 (22 cps) (F5 batch). Even with this polymer the desired f2 value was not achieved. The effect of these polymers on the release of acetazolamide from the capsules is shown in the following graph (**Fig 2**).

The F6 batch was formulated with Eudragit NE40D (15%). The desired f_2 value was not achieved with this batch also. The effect of Eudragit NE40D on the release of acetazolamide from the capsules is shown in the following graph (**Fig 3**). Acetazolamide in combination with Avicel was found to have excellent binding properties. The F7 and F8 batches were taken with only Avicel PH102 and Avicel PH101 respectively. The desired f_2 value was not achieved with these batches also. The effect of Avicel on the release of acetazolamide from the capsules is shown in the following graph (**Fig 4**). The F9 batch was formulated with Eudragit RL 30D (10%) and HPMC E5 (5%). The F10 batch was formulated with Eudragit RS 30D (10%) and HPMC E5 (5%). Both Eudragit RS 30D and Eudragit RL 30D are pH independent sustained release polymers. The release of drug from the capsules was much less than that of the innovator. The desired f_2 value was not achieved with these formulations also. The effect of these polymers on the release of acetazolamide from the capsules is shown in the following graph (**Fig 5**)¹¹.

Eudragit RL100 and Eudragit RS100 are insoluble in aqueous media but they are permeable and both have pH-independent release profiles. The permeability of Eudragit RS100 and RL100 in aqueous media is due to the presence of quaternary ammonium groups in their structure; Eudragit RL100 has a greater proportion of these groups and as such is more permeable than Eudragit RS100. The combinations of these polymers in different proportions provide varied sustained release profiles. Therefore the subsequent batches were

planned with different concentrations of these polymers.

The F11, F12, F13, F14, F15 and F16 batches were taken with different concentrations of Eudragit RS100 and Eudragit RL100. The F11 batch was formulated with Eudragit RS100 (7%) and Eudragit RL100 (3%). The F12 batch was formulated with Eudragit RS100 (6%) and Eudragit RL100 (4%). The F13 batch was formulated with Eudragit RS100 (4%) and Eudragit RL100 (6%). The F14 batch was formulated with Eudragit RS100 (5%) and Eudragit RL100 (5%). Finally, the F15 batch was formulated with Eudragit RS100 (10%) only. The F16 batch was taken with Eudragit RS100 (5%) and Eudragit EPO (5%). The effect of these polymers on the release of acetazolamide from the capsules is shown in the following graph (**Fig 6**). The effect of Eudragit RS100 (6%) and Eudragit RL100 (4%) (F12 batch) on the release of acetazolamide from the capsules is shown in the following graph. This formulation was found to obtain f_2 value of 69.70 and therefore this formula was decided to be the comparable formulation (**Fig 7**).

Release Mechanism

Based on the “n” value of 0.6094 obtained for F12 formulation, the drug release was found to follow Anomalous (non-Fickian) diffusion. This value indicates a coupling of the diffusion and erosion mechanism (Anomalous diffusion) and indicates that the drug release was controlled by more than one process. Based on the value of “n” ($n=0.6803$) for innovators product, it was also found to follow the

Table 4: Drug Release Kinetics

BATCH	ZERO ORDER		FIRST ORDER		HIGUCHI	
	r^2	K_0 (mg/L/hr)	r^2	K_1 (h^{-1})	r^2	K_{Hg} (h^{-1})
INNOVATO R	0.8167	5.0277	0.9962	0.206809	0.9849	25.163
F1	0.8632	3.8274	0.9796	0.089817	0.9838	18.972
F2	0.8435	3.76	0.9566	0.084059	0.9658	18.682
F3	0.8659	4.2393	0.9473	0.163282	0.9868	21.014
F4	0.2771	2.7199	0.3231	0.128737	0.5849	17.776
F5	0.5521	3.3103	0.7207	0.087514	0.8281	18.824
F6	0.8299	1.8353	0.8812	0.024642	0.9829	9.3138
F7	0.9132	3.0349	0.9603	0.051356	0.9706	14.528
F8	0.9256	2.0603	0.964	0.027175	0.9935	9.9112
F9	0.8433	1.758	0.8833	0.022339	0.9811	8.7991
F10	0.8118	3.832	0.9687	0.093041	0.9789	19.538
F11	0.8934	4.0669	0.9454	0.088895	0.9692	19.669
F12	0.8362	4.8148	0.9956	0.164894	0.9593	23.946
F13	0.6996	4.7354	0.9006	0.251717	0.9091	25.064
F14	0.4162	3.462	0.4495	0.139331	0.7049	20.92
F15	0.7939	4.23	0.9099	0.098107	0.9446	21.424
F16	0.9173	1.5704	0.9849	0.019345	0.999	7.6098

* r^2 = Correlation coefficient; K = Kinetic constant; n= Diffusional exponent.

Table 5: Drug Release Kinetics (contd.)

BATCH	KORSMEYER- PEPPAS		f2 value	$T_{50\%}$	$T_{75\%}$	$T_{90\%}$
	r^2	n				
INNOVATOR	0.9566	0.6803	-	5	8	12
F1	0.9704	0.4069	37.94339	7	8	12
F2	0.9429	0.4226	36.37011	7	8	13
F3	0.9641	0.3726	43.86922	5	10	18
F4	0.6135	0.0581	17.61706	<1	<1	<1
F5	0.9112	0.2516	35.33344	2	6	-
F6	0.9978	0.3869	16.76463	-	-	-
F7	0.9586	0.4694	23.4409	10	-	-
F8	0.9848	0.6603	15.59202	-	-	-
F9	0.9743	0.5629	15.01946	-	-	-
F10	0.9936	0.4132	42.80014	5	12	-
F11	0.9836	0.5836	35.00303	8	12	-
F12	0.9601	0.6094	69.70331	5	8	18
F13	0.9272	0.4573	42.44476	4	5	8
F14	0.6891	0.2399	24.22079	2	3	3
F15	0.9352	0.67	47.88738	5	9	-
F16	0.9983	0.50	13.09687	-	-	-

Same release mechanism. Also, the drug release mechanism was best explained by first order equation, as the plots showed the highest linearity ($r^2 = 0.9956$), followed by Higuchi's equation ($r^2 = 0.9593$). As the drug release was best fitted in first order kinetics, it indicated that the rate of drug release is concentration dependent. Even the innovators product was found to follow the same pattern with highest linearity ($r^2 = 0.9962$) for first order equation. The "r" value for Higuchi plot was found to be 0.9593 indicating that drug release included diffusion as one of the release mechanisms^{12,13}.

No significant change was observed in the percentage drug dissolved after a storage period of 1 month at 40°C / 75 % RH and 2 months at 40°C / 75 % RH for Acetazolamide ER capsules 500 mg. No significant change was observed in the assay value of Acetazolamide ER capsules 500 mg, after a storage period of 1 month at 40°C / 75 % RH and 2 months at 40°C / 75 % RH (**Fig. 12 and Fig. 13**). From the above data it was evident that there was no significant change in the physical and chemical parameters of Acetazolamide ER capsules 500 mg during the stability studies conducted at 40°C & 75%RH for 1 month period and 2 months at 40°C & 75% RH

Table 6: Accelerated stability studies.

S. No.	Drug + Excipient	Category	Drug : Excipient	Parameter	Initial Value of Parameter	1 Condition	
						40°C+75%RH	60°C
						4 weeks	4 weeks
01.	Acetazolamide	Active	-	Moisture content	0.12	0.17	0.11
				Total Impurity	NIL	0.01	0.01
				Assay	100	99.8	99.7
02.	Acetazolamide+Avicel PH101	Diluent	1:1	Moisture content	0.14	0.13	0.37
				Total Impurity	0.06	0.02	0.01
				Assay	99.6	99.6	99.5
03.	Acetazolamide+Eudragit RS100	ER Polymer	1:1	Moisture content	1.45	4.19	1.46
				Total Impurity	0.004	0.03	0.03
				Assay	99.4	99.3	99.3
04	Acetazolamide+Eudragit RL100	ER Polymer	1:1	Moisture content	1.67	2.85	1.96
				Total Impurity	0.01	0.05	0.017
				Assay	99.6	99.6	99.5
05	Acetazolamide+SLS	Wetting agent	1:1	Moisture content	4.08	4.25	4.85
				Total Impurity	0.003	0.00	0.025
				Assay	99.7	99.6	99.6
06.	Acetazolamide+Talc	Lubricant	1:1	Moisture content	4.95	3.26	2.55
				Total Impurity	0.01	0.09	0.043
				Assay	99.5	99.4	99.4

Fig 1: Dissolution profile of Innovator, F1, F2 and F3 batches.

Fig 4: Dissolution profile of Innovator, F7

Fig 2: Dissolution profile of Innovator, F4 and F5 batches

Fig 5: Dissolution profile of Innovator, F9 and F8 batches. and F10 batches.

Fig 3: Dissolution profile of Innovator and F6 batches.

Fig 6: Dissolution profile of Innovator, F11, F12, F13, F14, F15 and F16 batches.

Fig 7: Dissolution profile of Innovator and F12 batches.

Fig 8: Zero order plot for optimized formulation.

Fig 9: First order plot for optimized formulation.

Fig 10: Higuchi order plot for optimized formulation.

Fig 11: Peppas curve for optimized formulation.

Fig. 12: Accelerated stability studies-Dissolution

Fig. 13: Accelerated stability studies-Assay.

CONCLUSION

The aim of the present study was to develop an extended release formulation of Acetazolamide to maintain constant therapeutic levels of the drug for over 12 hrs. An efficient extended release formulation of Acetazolamide could be designed as extended release capsules. The optimised formulation (F12) was developed by using Eudragit RS100 (6%) and Eudragit RL100 (4%). Regulated drug release in first order manner was attained by using these polymers¹⁴. This extended release formulation (F12) was found similar and comparable to the innovator product based on the f_2 value (69.70) obtained. The developed extended release capsule formulation was quite stable with regard to drug content, physical properties and dissolution rate in the accelerated stability studies.

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